

A Hospital Based Observational Assessment of Prevalence and Symptoms in Patients with Eosinophilia Using Peripheral Smear Method

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The present study aimed to evaluate the prevalence and symptoms in patients with eosinophilia.

Methods: The study was done in Department of Pathology, Madhubani Medical College & Hospital, Madhubani and Tertiary care hospital Madhubani, Bihar, India. It was done for one year. The study included total of 100 patients based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All the patients were explained study protocol and informed consent was obtained.

Results: The study included 100 patients. 25 patients were in the age group of 41-50 years. 22 patients were between 51-60 years. 3 patients in each had age between 1-10 and 2 patients in 81-90 years. Male (n=60) were more compared to females (n=40) in this study. A total of 21 symptoms observed in the study population. Fever was the most common (n=20) symptom compared to others. 14 patients showed cough and 12 had breathlessness. 10 had chest pain and 10 had skin lesions. Least number of patients showed hemoptysis, hydrocele, headache, bleeding pepr rectum and history of snake bite. 60 patients in mild, 30 in moderate and 10 in severe eosinophilia categories were observed in this study.

Conclusion: The study showed middle age with male sex is more prone to eosinophilia. Fever and cough are the most common symptoms.

Keywords: Blood, Eosinophilia, Age, Gender, Fever, Cough.

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Introduction

The typical percentage of blood eosinophils in healthy individuals is less than 5%.¹ Absolute eosinophil count can be determined by multiplying total white blood cell count by the percentage of eosinophils. Eosinophilia is considered when absolute eosinophil count exceeds 500/ μ L in peripheral blood. Eosinophilia can be categorized as mild (absolute eosinophil count ranges from 500/ μ L to 1,500/ μ L), moderate (absolute eosinophil count ranges from 1,500/ μ L to 5,000/ μ L),

or severe (absolute eosinophil count >5,000/ μ L). [2] Peripheral blood eosinophilia can be caused by parasitic infections, allergy, drug reactions, leukemia, and non-hematologic cancers. [1]

The urgency for the evaluation of eosinophilia depends on the presence and the degree of tissue and/or organ involvement. There are many reports of acutely ill patients with extremely high eosinophil count or outpatients with signs

of organ involvement. [3-6] However, eosinophilia might be discovered as an incidental finding based on complete blood count in an otherwise healthy individual. Because eosinophilia in such situation is rarely reported, collective features of incidental eosinophilia have not been clearly delineated.

Mild or moderate increase in the blood eosinophil count detected from the differential leukocyte count may be met with during routine health screening as an isolated laboratory abnormality without an apparent association with the disease or as an epiphenomenon during a diagnostic work up for an illness. [7-9] However in the modern literature, a little work has been done in the field of blood eosinophilia. In patients with eosinophilia, it is prudent to have a thorough investigation performed to diagnose and rule out underlying systemic disease. [10,11] The diagnostic work up of patients with eosinophilia remains controversial as there are no definite symptoms and no definite cause can be diagnosed in most cases. [12]

The present study aimed to evaluate the prevalence and symptoms in patients with eosinophilia.

Methods

The study was done in Department of Pathology, Madhubani Medical College & Hospital, Madhubani, Bihar, India. It was done for one year. The study included total of 100 patients based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. All the patients were explained study protocol and informed consent was obtained. The patient's blood was collected and used for peripheral smear examination. Demographic, clinical and pathological data was recorded and analysed.

Inclusion criteria

- Both gender
- **Absolute** Eosinophil count more than 500/mm³
- No other hematological disorders

Exclusion criteria

- Critically ill
- Recent infection
- Any recent major surgery

Statistical analysis: The data was expressed in number and percentage. Microsoft excel 2019 used for the calculation of percentage and drawing the graphs.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of patients based on the age and gender

Age groups in years	N	%
1-10	3	3
11-20	7	7
21-30	7	7
31-40	12	12
41-50	25	25
51-60	22	22
61-70	12	12
71-80	10	10
81-90	2	2
Gender		
Male	60	60
Female	40	40

The study included 100 patients. 25 patients were in the age group of 41-50 years. 22 patients were between 51-60 years. 3 patients in each had age between 1-10 and 2 patients in 81-90 years. Male (n=60) were more compared to females (n=40) in this study.

Table 2: Distribution of patients based on the symptoms

Symptoms	Number
Fever	20
Cough	14
Breathlessness	12
Chest pain	10
Skin lesion	10
Feature of psychosis	7
Edema	7
Neurological symptoms	6
Body pain	6
Vomiting	5
Abdominal pain	5
Alcohol abuse	3
Tiredness	2
Menorrhagia	1
Loss of appetite	1
Preoperative check up	1
Hemoptysis	1
Hydrocele	1
Headache	1
Bleeding per rectum	1
History of snake bite	1

A total of 21 symptoms observed in the study population. Fever was the most common (n=20) symptom compared to others. 14 patients showed cough and 12 had breathlessness. 10 had chest pain and 10 had skin lesions. Least number of patients showed hemoptysis, hydrocele, headache, bleeding per rectum and history of snake bite.

Table 3: Distribution of patients based on the eosinophil count

Type	N
Mild	60
Moderate	30
Severe	10

60 patients in mild, 30 in moderate and 10 in severe eosinophilia categories were observed in this study.

Discussion

The study aimed at elaborating the prevalence and symptoms associated with peripheral blood eosinophilia in a total of 100 patients and detailed history was taken, a complete examination including general and systemic examination carried

out, and a series of investigations including complete peripheral smear examination was done.

Eosinophilia was more prevalent in males in our study. Majority fell into the age group of 41-50 years. Patients presented with multiple nonspecific symptoms involving various organ systems. In 25 out of 100 patients (25%), eosinophilia could not be attributed to any specific etiology. This figure corresponds to the 34% of

patients with undetermined etiology in Kobisade et al.'s study of 100 hospitalized patients with eosinophilia and 36% of patients with undetermined etiology in Brigden and Graydon's study of 225 outpatient cases of eosinophilia. [13,14]

In the study by Anshumakkar et al [15], this corresponded to 70% of patients. 4.3% of the cases of peripheral blood eosinophilia were attributed to asthma in our study. Asthma or other atopic diseases was the cause of eosinophilia in 13% of the cases according to previous study. In a recent study by Lombardi and Passalacqua on 1862 patients with eosinophilia, 80% of the cases were found to be associated with atopic diseases. [16] A study conducted by Bousquet J et al. on 43 patients with chronic asthma found that peripheral blood eosinophilia is associated with severity of asthma. [17] The present study also showed similar results. Exfoliative dermatitis was implicated to be the cause of eosinophilia in 5.2% of the patients in our study group. A number of dermatological conditions like exfoliative dermatitis, atopic dermatitis, eosinophilic cellulitis are associated with eosinophilia. Lombardi and Passalacqua [16] had attributed eosinophilia to skin diseases in 2.1% of the patients and Kobisade et al. [13], in 3% of cases. The study results showed fever is the most common symptom compared to others. [18]

Conclusion

Eosinophilia is one of the commonest blood disorders. The study results concluded that eosinophilia is most common in middle aged males. The most common symptom among the patients was fever followed by cough and breathlessness. Early detection and initiation of treatment can reduce the progression of disease.

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